

Inaugural RSC ROI Local Section Retired Members Networking Event

Report by: F D Austin

Event Date: 12/03/2025

Venue: Ivy Restaurant, Dawson St,
Dublin

Event Type: Networking Event

Report received: 11/04/2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15198720

<http://zenodo.org/communities/ice/>

Organising Committee: Dave Austin, CChem FRSC (Retired)

Event Sponsor

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section

Summary

The RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section committee were looking to increase the type of events that it offered to members and looked at other local section activities for inspiration. Networking events for retired members had been carried out by some other local sections and it was decided to try this for 2024. Unfortunately there was insufficient interest as the invite went out with the Christmas card. The committee choose to send an e-card for Christmas 2024 with the invite and this allowed an e-alert follow up message in January 2025. This follow up proved decisive in generating enough interest to host an event in 2025. A lunch venue in Dublin was chosen to facilitate the inaugural networking event for retired members who travelled form far and wide across the country gathered at the Ivy Restaurant. People attended from Dublin, Cork, Clare, Tipperary and Waterford. This inaugural networking event was successful, with hopes expressed to repeat this type of event in the future. The attendees saw value in attending other Local Section events where their experience could be leveraged by members earlier in their careers.

Attendees

Attendees were from academia and industry. A number of universties were represented as well as industries such as quality control, pharmaceuticals, manufacturing and the oil industry.

Feedback

Everyone present at the event appreciated the opportunity to meet and connect with other retired members of the RSC ROI Local Section and agreed to allow their emails to be used to continue to share information and stay connected. Afterwards several attendees sent correspondence in appreciation of the event and expressing the hope that other events could be organised in the future for this cohort of members.

Acknowledgements

I would like to acknowledge the RSC Republic of Ireland local section committee for their support and encouragement in delivering this inaugural retired member networking event.